

Data Collectives

A practical guide to experimentation

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Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction to Data Collectives	4
1.1 What is a Data Collective?	4
1.2 Legal Structures and Terminology	8
1.3 How does a Data Collective function?	11
1.4 How Data Collectives Pursue Change	13
2. Motivations and Methodologies	19
2.1 What is the value data collectives achieve from data?	19
2.2 Why are collectives more able to get value from data?	21
Barriers to Individual Agency and Negotiability	22
How Collectives Can Help Challenge These Barriers	23
Other ways for collectives to get value from data	25
2.3 Three Philosophies for Collectives	26
Capitalist Collectives	26
‘Common Good’ Collectives	27
Individualist Collectives	29
2.4 Three Paradigms of Collective Work	31
Investigative	31
Educational	32
Activist	33
3. The Impacts of Data Collectives	35
3.1 WhoTargetsMe: Pursuing Algorithmic Accountability	35
3.2 Max Schrems v Facebook: Improved Individual Rights	37
3.3 Uber Drivers: From fairer working conditions to rethinking mobility	40
3.4 MIDATA and other Health Data Coops	45
3.5 Citizen Science and the Zooniverse	47
4. Enabling and Nurturing Data Collectives	51
4.1 Enabling Collective Action Through Data	52
4.2 Approaches to Supporting Collectives and Data Collectives	54
Individual/Internal (“Educate & Empower”)	54
Individual/External (“Influence & Motivate”)	55
Collective/Internal (“Learn & Discover”)	56
Collective/External (“Defend & Create”)	57
4.3 Extending a Data Collective’s Reach and Potential Impact	57

4.4 The Data Enablement Cube: A model for supporting data collectives to flourish
59

5. Funding and Sustainability **62**

6. Recommendations **63**

Executive Summary

In today's digital world, data is power, and how its used can significantly impact society. This guide introduces the concept of "data collectives" as a new way for groups of people to come together and harness the power of data for collective benefit. A data collective is a group that pools personal data to achieve shared goals, like improving rights, promoting transparency, or advancing scientific research. Unlike tech companies that often use data for profit, data collectives focus on benefiting their members or society as a whole.

We start by defining what a data collective is and exploring the different ways they can be organized. We then discuss why data collectives are uniquely positioned to unlock value from data that individuals might struggle to achieve on their own. Through real-world examples like initiatives for fairer working conditions for Uber drivers, citizen science projects, and efforts to hold companies accountable for data practices, we demonstrate the powerful impact data collectives can have.

The guide also provides practical advice on how to create and support a data collective, from securing funding to building sustainable models for long-term success. We offer a framework for thinking about how to support these groups effectively, emphasizing the importance of collaboration, innovation, and community engagement.

Data collectives are a promising way to give people more control over their data and create positive change. By working together, these groups can tackle big challenges, make better use of data, and ensure that its benefits are more fairly distributed.

1. Introduction to Data Collectives

1.1 What is a Data Collective?

In order to define a data collective, we must first define a collective.

In the paper "*Collectives: Compositional protocols for contributions and returns*"¹, mathematicians Niu and Spivak offer a precise mathematical definition of a collective:

¹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.11518>

A collective is an **interface** with a **protocol** for **aggregating contributions** and **distributing returns**. It has four parts:

1. A set of contributions;
2. For each contribution, a set of returns;
3. A mechanism for aggregating contributions;
4. A mechanism for distributing the returns.

The interface is the place at which the contribution and return mechanisms operate.

The protocol is the agreed rules or available workflows which constitute these mechanisms.

To de-formalise this definition and help us move towards defining *data* collectives specifically, we can consider the following:

- A **contribution** might be 'sharing some of your personal data with the collective', but could be the provision of a service related to data.
- A **return** could be some benefit you get for participating in the collective (for example, insights inferred from analysis of the collective's pool of shared data).
- **Aggregating contributions** simply means the combining of data, when we are talking about data contributions. Many collectives work on the idea of producing a shared pool of members' data from which comparisons and insights can be made.
- An **interface** might be 'the website you use to interact with the collective' (but could also be a person, a communication channel, or an app).
- A **protocol** might be the procedure you follow to upload your data, the procedure to request data deletion from the collective pool, or more interestingly the procedure used to define which return to others you might find acceptable.

We will return to this functional view of the parts of a collective in Section 1.2. For this section, let us now consider a more practical view of what a collective, and specifically a data collective is likely to look like from the outside, and what role it might play in today's data-centric society.

Less formally, a collective is generally accepted to be *a group of individuals or organisations who come together and pool their resources to work towards at least one*

common purpose or shared objective. Collectives can refer to communities or interest groups, as well as creative collaborations or worker cooperatives (an alternative to traditional hierarchical business models where members have greater involvement in organisational decision making). But what is a data collective, then?

We define a (personal) *data* collective as follows:

A collective can be considered as a (personal) data collective if and only if these two things are both true:

- i) the collective uses **personal data as a resource**,
- ii) the collective is concerned with **a duty to the data subject**.

The following **may** also be true, but these are not required for the collective to already be considered a (personal) data collective²:

- iii) some of the collective's members contribute their **own personal data**,
- iv) the collective pursues **data-related benefits** to these **data subjects**.

Many data collectives have objectives related to personal data usage and rights (for example, using personal data to obtain better platform rights or employee rights), but others use personal data to pursue other objectives, such as supporting health goals, addressing environmental concerns, or improving democratic accountability.³

In a data collective, the members of the group *pool* or *donate* the personal data they hold, so that it may be analysed, compared or aggregated. The data becomes a shared resource of the group, for use towards a collective goal. Key to data collectives is the idea that **value can be extracted from data**, and that through pooling and collaborative work on the data, value can be obtained that **could not be obtained otherwise**. The

² The authors view these last two properties as contributing to a form of purity to the data collective considered, but in the current practice it seems to currently be near impossible to achieve. Note also that these properties can be achieved by considering the set of actors wide enough: if some stakeholders contribute someone else's personal data, one might simply need to expand the range of actors involved to include all those along the data processing chain.

³ See the Data Governance Act, and its definition of data altruism as "the consent by data subjects to process personal data pertaining to them [...] for purposes of general interest, such as scientific research purposes or improving public services;"

specific nature of this value will be explored in Section 2.1. Another important element of data collectives is that personal data is shared **for a specific purpose**, for the benefit of the group, its cause, or its members. Collectives will usually keep and use data for those specific purposes, whereas in a commercial context collected data is often used in secondary ways (such as selling it for profit or exploiting it for advertising).

Some might argue that data collectives should be defined more broadly, and could include almost any endeavour where people come together around data. We generally reject this broad interpretation, and reduce the scope with the two compulsory conditions (i) and (ii) described above. It is true that the sacrifice of personal data into shared spaces or platforms is commonplace, now that much of the world we inhabit is encoded as data. For example, would we consider Facebook Groups to be a data collective? Or an online community such as those seen on Reddit, Strava, Flickr or Ancestry.com - places where people gather to collaborate with data? Sometimes, such examples can be useful as points of reference when thinking about collective activity or ways of organising a group. Indeed in Section 3.5 we do refer to a collective, Zooniverse, that is not strictly a *data* collective by our own definition. Even where a collective's members are not focused on or paying attention to personal data that is contributed or generated and the members are there for some other reason, it may still be insightful to examine that collective. In the main, we will focus on data collectives where personal data storage and usage and the duty of care to its use and holding is a primary focus of the collective.

Considering now what data collectives **do**, we generalise that collectives perform either **one OR both** of two key features:

- 1) The **acquisition of knowledge** through pooling, comparison and shared analysis of data.
- 2) **Using shared knowledge** to attempt to produce change in thinking or behaviour from others - which can encompass education, influencing corporate or governmental practices, or pursuing social change.

Typically, we think of data collectives in the context of socially minded groups of individuals working to achieve some benefit for society or for themselves as individuals, but as we will see there are other legitimate models of data collective too that we should also encompass in our definition - for example, two data-holding organisations working together to compare and augment their customer data. In this case, the collective is still concerned with personal data and using it as a resource - but this is not the members'

own data, rather than that of their customers. And there is still a duty of care to the data subject; but in this case that duty becomes a consideration for the collective to abide by in its activities, rather than a direct objective for the collective. This example is useful to show how even sticking within requirements (i) and (ii), there are still a wide variety of possible types of data collective.

1.2 Legal Structures and Terminology

One key aspect of our definition of a data collective, is that we deliberately **avoid prescribing a particular legal, technical or social structure**. This is useful, because many different schools of thought around this space are emerging, and it is a space of rapid change, so it is more helpful to talk about the general phenomenon than to attach ourselves to a particular infrastructure or mental model.

Already existing defined structures around data collaboration include:

Data Trust. A data trust is a third party service provider, who offers ‘*independent, fiduciary stewardship of personal data*’⁴. In other words, it is an organisation whose sole and primary purpose is to keep data safely on behalf of its users. The data trust has legal obligations to treat clients impartially and to look after their data with transparency, loyalty and prudent security and privacy protections. Typically users of a data trust pay a fee for storage and safekeeping of their data. Data trusts are not inherently collectives. Collectives may however choose to use a data trust to hold data on their member’s behalf. Conversely, a data trust may also function as a collective, in some cases, holding data for its own members to make use of.

Data Foundation. Trusts are legal instruments only present in the common law world, and their closest equivalent for civil law might be constituted as a foundation. However it gets quite subtle in extreme cases, in how responsibility is managed once things go wrong.⁵

⁴ <https://web.archive.org/web/20210625175131/https://theodi.org/article/what-is-a-data-trust/>

⁵ An unfortunate example comes from Switzerland, where the government encouraged the establishment of a private foundation, mesvaccins.ch, to help manage vaccination data on a voluntary basis into some kind of “health wallet”. This was combined with public interest considerations around research on vaccine coverage etc. However, with the pressures of COVID, the foundation went bankrupt. Swiss laws mandated that the foundation cover its debt by selling beneficiaries’ data. This was avoided, fortunately, on a technicality, despite the creditors’ interests trumping those of the beneficiaries of the service (i.e. the data subject).

Data co-operative. A data co-operative is a term for a specific type of data collective, though it is often used quite broadly. Simply put, it is an organisation where the members of the organisation contribute their own data into a pool that they collectively own, and use it to pursue their own agenda. For example, data cooperatives could be an effective way to pursue women's empowerment⁶. In other data collectives, those contributing data may no longer maintain ownership over the data once they donate it, or the organisation might not be arranged as a cooperative with equal member voting rights.

Data trusts, data foundations and data cooperatives are examples of '**data institutions**'. The ODI have an information page about these⁷.

Data coalition. A data coalition represents a union or coalition between different data collectives, companies or data institutions, who configure shared pools or flows of data between themselves for the common goals or mutual benefits of the participating member groups. An examples is *RadicalxChange*, which aims to connect progressive personal data-related organisations around the world⁸. Another example of data coalition is seen between *Hestia.ai* and *personaldata.io*, or between Hestia.ai and Sitra in the digipower project, where particular systems, rules and processes are put in place to carefully share data, with consent, for particular purposes.

Data lockers, also known as personal data lockers, personal data stores (PDS), personal data vaults (PDV), or personal information management services, (PIMS) are a physical infrastructure that allows the collection and storage of personal data. In other words 'a *place to put your personal data*'. Once your data is in the PDS, as well as individuals gaining *MyData* or *Personal Informatics*⁹ type benefits for themselves, their data can be licenced for use by third parties, using consent mechanisms such as digi.me's Private Sharing¹⁰ model. Typically personal data lockers serve only a single user, not a collective, although there are exceptions, such as BBC R&D's recent *Together+ DataPod* trial, which allowed members of a watch party to collect view data generated by their viewing together¹¹. Personal data lockers do not have any specific legal obligations or business model, they might operate like a data trust, or might be focused on some other

⁶ <https://data2x.org/how-data-cooperative-structures-can-support-womens-empowerment/>

⁷ <https://web.archive.org/web/20210619222626/https://theodi.org/project/rd-data-institutions/>

⁸ <https://www.radicalxchange.org/about/>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1145/1753326.1753409>

¹⁰ <https://digi.me/feature-consent>

¹¹ <https://www.bbc.co.uk/taster/pilots/bbc-together>

purpose, such as productivity tracking¹² or selling one's own data¹³. You can draw an analogy to services like Dropbox or Google Drive, but the difference is that with personal data lockers there is a greater focus on the data itself, individual agency and control (in line with the MyData idea of being in control of one's own data ecosystem¹⁴).

Collective intelligence, while not a specific type of data institution or infrastructure, is another relevant term here. This refers to the ability of a collective (in this case often a data collective) to use their knowledge and abilities to solve problems together. This is done through collaboration, coordination or communication among the groups. The term focuses on the ability of the group to work together, rather than on the sharing of data itself. For an example of some data collectives that classify themselves in terms of their collective intelligence rather than their organisational infrastructure, see the directory of the Civic Tech Field Guide¹⁵.

Collective Action is a similar concept to collective intelligence, but refers to the external functions that a collective is able to execute rather than its internal effectively; this concept will be fully explained and explored in section 2.4 (under the Activist paradigm).

As we have shown, many different terms, structures and functions exist when considering data collectives. In this report, we deliberately do not adhere to any one mental model when defining a data collective. In doing so, we can draw inspiration from a wide variety of examples, and explore different aspects of data collectives, without constraint. We examine data collectives as a phenomenon, and the commonalities they have that span the many different configurations of data collective. By including reference to some more well-established collectives which are not obviously data collectives, we can draw useful insights and inspiration that data collectives can learn from.

¹² <https://magicflow.com/>

¹³ <https://datacy.com/consumer>

¹⁴ <https://www.mydata.org/participate/declaration/>

¹⁵ <https://civictech.guide/about/>

1.3 How does a Data Collective function?

Turning back to Niu and Spivak's formal definition of a collective introduced at the start of Section 1.1, we can now dive a little bit 'inside' the concept of a collective. By refining this general definition and switching our focus to consider the functional components that constitute a data collective, we can more easily talk about them in a structured way.

In interpreting the theoretical model of a collective, we can define the components of a data collective in a way that will provide a useful reference in this report. Most commonly, the contribution would be some personal data and the return would be some insights derived from use of the **pooled personal data**, motivating the contributor in the first place. But there are exceptions to these generalisations:

- Individuals may make other contributions, such as **money, time, or brainpower**, in exchange for some return.
- As mentioned above, members might **not be individuals** - for example a company might contribute insights from its customers' data into a collective pool, or a data collective might share its members' personal data with another collective for an agreed purpose in order to deliver additional returns to the members of both collectives.
- Contributors may not receive any direct return for their contribution, as **their contribution may benefit others** (for example, an altruistic contribution where the return is distributed to other members of society).

By defining the components of a data collective in terms of the same functional components of **interfaces, protocols, contributions** and **returns**, we now have a lens through which we can consider different data collectives and draw insights from how they operate, and compare and contrast different collectives more easily by comparison of their components. This will allow them to be understood more deeply so that the reader can apply this knowledge to other collective efforts with data.

An important part of the framing of the definition we have presented across Sections 1.1 and 1.2 is that we do not wish to impose specific ideas on how a data collective should organise its infrastructure and members. Instead, we abstract away the practical differences between how data collectives operate, and focus on their **functional** components.

Let us now clarify each of these functional components:

An interface refers to any ‘membrane’¹⁶ of the collective through which its members or other parties might interact with it. This could involve web locations such as a signup form, a data-viewing portal, a button to donate data or money, or a smartphone app, but could also involve communication-related channels such as a postal address, phone number, social media channel or chatroom. Typically a data collective will have at least an interface for uploading or gathering data, and an interface for accessing what the collective has been learning or doing with that collective data pool.

A protocol refers to the specific processes through which data is received, pooled, analysed/used and published. For example, there might be a protocol for anonymising data at the point of upload, and there might be a protocol by which data is cleaned, analysed or annotated after upload. There may also be specific protocols in place to access services or support tasks for members (e.g. data deletion) or external actors (e.g. a press request), or to decide what goals the collective should be pursuing.

Member contributions are the things that members put into the collective. Typically this will be one of four things - data, money, time/brainpower, or decisions. In some data collectives (especially in citizen science or on shared research platforms), some members take a more *passive* role in the collective, donating their data and leaving others to do the analysis. In other cases, especially in data cooperatives or those collectives where some members are highly technically skilled or expert in data-processing, such members can take a more *active* role, not only contributing data but taking part in the collaborative work of extracting value from the data pool too. As mentioned at the start of this paragraph, data need not be involved for a contribution to be relevant. Data collectives need funding, and the donation of funds from individuals or research organisations would still count as a contribution.

Distributed returns are the benefits that contributors receive; for example insights, profits from the licensing of data, skills and education, or personal utility from acquiring new capabilities over their pooled personal data. Note that not all benefits or outputs of a collective are ‘returns’; for example a collective may create impacts upon data holding organisations, or upon policymakers or regulators, or societal benefits. For this reason, we do sometimes identify **other external benefits** of a data collective’s activity.

¹⁶ We use the word ‘membrane’ instead of ‘surface’ or ‘edge’ because we wish to include the notion that the collective can ‘let things through’ (contributions and returns).

1.4 How Data Collectives Pursue Change

In this section, we introduce an important mental model for considering how collectives and data collectives work towards their goals: through the pursuit of change - change in understanding, knowledge, thinking, behaviours, structures, procedures or relationships.

The four-quadrant model we present below is an application of the concepts of *Theory of Change (ToC)* to the specific problem space of data collectives. This mental scaffold can assist in thinking about how to work with collectives and data collectives. In Section 4, we develop this mental model further, such that it can be used like a business strategy tool, where a given collective's current activities, capabilities and impact can be assessed, and opportunities for support and growth identified accordingly.

Before describing the assistance that an organisation could provide to a data collective in order to grow within *the wider business & societal ecosystem*, let us first look inside from the data collective's own perspective outwards, at the work it can do to effect change - which is any collective's ultimate goal.

Figure 1: Theory of Change [ToC]: The Four Dimensions of Change¹⁷

¹⁷ Diagram used here unchanged from 'Hivos ToC Guidelines: Theory of Change Thinking in Practice'. by Es, Guijt and Vogel (2015, p. 90, The Hague, NL) under a CC-BY-NC-SA 3.0 licence. The authors state that this

Theories of Change (ToC) is a set of methodologies commonly used by philanthropists, educators and those trying to improve the lives of disadvantaged populations¹⁸. The theories can be used in different ways including planning, participatory design and field evaluation of the effectiveness of new initiatives. There are different implementations but most focus on explicitly mapping out desired outcomes¹⁹ with a clear focus on who is acting and whether the change being brought about is a **change in action, or a change in thinking**¹⁵. Figure 1 shows how the pursuit of change can be usefully mapped out on two axes: Individual/Collective and Internal/External.

According to ToC theory, desired changes can be broken down into:

- **Internal changes:** changes in thinking, feeling, reasoning, understanding, attitudes or identity.
- **External changes:** changes in actions, behaviour, interactions, structure, policy, technological capability, processes and the external environment.

At the same time, desired changes can be broken down into:

- **Individual changes:** changes to individual thought or actions
- **Collective changes:** changes to the thoughts or actions of groups of people together, or to the systems, practices and norms of society at large.

These two splits produce four dimensions of change, and form four quadrants representing different types of change, which are shown in Figure 1 and described here:

- **Individual/Internal (II):** This top-left quadrant represents changes to what individuals know and understand, and to how they think, feel and plan to act.
- **Individual/External (IE):** This top-right quadrant represents changes to how individuals' relationships with others; acting (or being enabled to act) differently in their daily lives and when interacting within society.
- **Collective/Internal (CI):** This bottom-left quadrant represents changes in the shared knowledge of groups of people or to the collective identity or values of social groups.

diagram was adapted from earlier work by Wilber (1996), Keystone (2008) and Retolaza (2010, 2012). <https://hivos.org/resource/hivos-guidelines-theory-change-thinking-practice/>

¹⁸ Brest, Paul. "The power of theories of change." (2010): 47-51.

¹⁹ Taplin, D. H. and Clark, H. (2012) *Theory of change basics: A primer on theory of change*, ActKnowledge, p. 9. http://www.theoryofchange.org/wp-content/uploads/toco_library/pdf/ToCBasics.pdf.

- **Collective/External (CE):** This bottom-right quadrant represents changes to the structures and procedures within which people operate, including technology, law, societal norms and communications.

Key to ToC thinking is the idea that making changes in one quadrant can stimulate change in others; for example:

1. Collective learning about data attitudes and practices, such as the research conducted in the digipower project (lower left quadrant).
2. This learning could inform the design of new technologies, interfaces or processes (such as the data viewing tools of digipower.academy) (lower right quadrant).
3. If organisations were funded to build these designs, this could make new structures available to have an impact on improving individual-provider relationship (service users might begin seeing their data and data relationships in new ways through use of the tools, fuelling new demands to providers) (upper-right quadrant).
4. The changes to those relationships could then in turn lead to individuals thinking and feeling differently (upper left quadrant), for example feeling more empowered or having greater awareness of data practices.

In his thesis²⁰ Alex Bowyer applies the ToC model to the personal data economy/power landscape, considering how these quadrants could be embraced by data collectives and others interested in improving in what he calls human data relations (HDR) – the ways in which people relate to data and to organisations that hold their data – as shown in Figure 2 below.

²⁰ Thesis: *Understanding and Improving Human Data Relations*, Alex Bowyer, Newcastle University (2023,). Chapter 9: Practical Approaches to Improve Human Data Relations

Figure 2: Model of how ToC theory can be applied to the problem of increasing individual agency and negotiability in the personal data economy landscape (source: Alex Bowyer²⁰)

Approaches for considering what activities can be best applied in each quadrant are detailed in Chapter 9 of his thesis, which is relevant reading for the reader. However, we include the key points here; the activities that should take place in each quadrant for a collective to achieve its desired changes are pictured in Figure 2 and summarised here:

- **Learn & Discover (CI):** In this quadrant, individuals, researchers, activists and other stakeholders work in groups to understand data attitudes and user needs, and to *gain collective knowledge* of data collection and usage practices which are sometimes hidden.
- **Defend & Create (CE):** In this quadrant, activists work to ensure current data access and rights *capabilities are not eroded*, while researchers, designers, technologists and social innovators *design and create new technologies*, operating models, organisations and interface designs, the structures enabling a world with more balanced individual and collective data capabilities.
- **Influence & Motivate (IE):** In this quadrant, individuals' relationships with data and with data holders, as well as data holders and policymakers' relationships, can be improved. For organisations like Sitra and for collectives, as actors seeking to change society, the task is to *influence the many parties to change by*

showcasing and facilitating newly created structures and capabilities, and to harness new collective knowledge to advocate the benefits of changing data-related behaviours.

- **Educate & Empower (II):** In this quadrant, *individuals' ways of thinking about data and data holders grow* as they begin to feel more aware and empowered. This would constitute definitive progress and impact for collectives. Such changes can be driven through education, improving personal data economy literacy, and through the experience of new capabilities and changed relationships with data and with data holders. Such changed relations could empower individuals to hold a more aware and equitable position in their digital lives.

The ToC model, expanded by Alex Bowyer's research, can offer a useful frame for data collectives to think about the ways in which they can effect change upon others and upon the world, in pursuit of their objectives.

So if this is how collectives themselves pursue change, what is the role of external organisations that wish to support data collectives. In short, the goal is to *increase a collective's ability to achieve the desired changes in each quadrant*. By focusing on a particular quadrant and the precise impacts or changes pursued, the support organisation and the collective itself can increase their *impact potential*.

In this regard collectives face many of the same challenges as any small organisation or startup: challenges with human resources, attracting users(members), funding, sustainability, scaling up, public relations, and increasing market share or reach.

A data collective might lack:

- Interest from members of the public who can join the collective and contribute data or time/effort;
- Funding, from individual donors or grant-awarding organisations;
- Novel business models that can generate sustainable revenue while preserving individual data consent and human-centric ideologies;
- Effective capabilities for internal management, project management, human resources, marketing, or other areas
- Hardware or software infrastructure to host data, services and web presence
- Skills in data analysis, software engineering, business development or strategy
- Connections to potential partner organisations
- Contacts with journalists, media, and public relations firms

- Any number of other normal organisational/business needs

Thus, increasing the collective's impact potential is something where an external organisation can clearly provide help in a number of ways. In much the same way as a venture capitalist supporting a startup, support can come in the form of money, business and strategic expertise, introductions and connections to other parties and businesses, as well as technical and business innovation, feedback and suggestions.

Structured approaches to providing such support, with the modified ToC framing in mind, are explored more thoroughly in section 4.

2. Motivations and Methodologies

In this section, we will explore what motivates data collectives, the philosophies that guide them, and how those objectives are pursued tangibly through the activities a collective undertakes.

2.1 What is the value data collectives achieve from data?

As explained in Section 1, a key purpose for data collectives is to achieve value derived from the data that it or its individual members hold. This can be understood further through the DIKW (data-information-knowledge-wisdom) pyramid, first presented by Ackoff in 1989. The pyramid expresses the idea that increasing value can be obtained from data through its interpretation as *information*, the accumulation and harnessing of that information to obtain *knowledge*, leading to the considered application of that knowledge embodying *wisdom*. The adaptation of the pyramid by Tedeschi in 2019, pictured below, conveys the different activities that occur at the different levels. In order to interpret data as information, context is needed. In order to acquire knowledge, additional meanings are needed, and in order to acquire wisdom, insights are required. The further up the pyramid you can go, the more complete your understanding will be, and therefore the more solidly grounded any actions or plans will be.

Figure 3: The path to wisdom, moving up Ackoff's DIKW pyramid²¹, adapted by Tedeschi²²

Data is, in essence, nothing more than a series of codes - be they marks on a page, or 1's and 0's in a computer file. Data is inherently ambiguous, as its encoding scheme or format is decided by certain individuals for a specific purpose. Its interpretation may rely on knowledge that was not included. It has been said that information can be thought of as the resolution of uncertainty. In this context, that first step from data to information can be thought of as *using data to answer a question*.

In general, those questions will concern one of two types of information that can be found from the data³:

- i) information about themselves and their lives - *life information*
- ii) information about the handling and use of their data - *data ecosystem information*

If we consider that data can provide information and answers, as well as having inherent value as something that can be kept, we can infer that there are four distinct roles²³ that data can serve to individuals, and hence to collectives:

²¹ Ackoff, R. L. (1989) *From data to wisdom*, Journal of Applied Systems Analysis, 16(1), pp. 3–9.

²² Tedeschi, Luis O. (2019) *Mathematical modelling in ruminant nutrition: approaches and paradigms, extant models, and thoughts for upcoming predictive analytics*, Journal of Animal Science 97.5, pp. 1921-1944.

²³ Bowyer, A (2022) *Understanding and Improving Human Data Relations*. Thesis, Newcastle University.

1. Data has a role as an *artefact of value* to people who hold it or which it pertains to (for example, your digital notes or photos);
2. Data has a role to *inform people* about themselves, the world, and about the actions of those who created and modified it;
3. Data has a role as a *usable material* with which to effect change in one's life or in the world (for example, as evidence of facts); and
4. Data has a role as a *means to monitor changes* in individual lives, in information landscapes, or in the actions of data-centric service organisations and digital platforms.

Given these different roles that data can play, it is possible to infer at least six different ways in which people can gain value from data:

1. *Acquiring possession* of their own data, so they might keep it and use it for their own ends;
2. *Increasing their understanding* of the information encoded within, and implied by, their data, by putting it in context or comparing it with others;
3. *Unifying and uniting their data* from different sources, to provide greater informational insights;
4. *Using data to learn about the behaviour of data holders* to enable accountability,
5. *Validating data against known realities*, to understand how they are seen through data and to identify unfair treatment or misleading information presentations;
6. *Transforming, shaping, summarising and visualising data* into forms that are more readily usable as evidence, shareable extracts, or understandable forms.

As the next section will show, all of these activities are more easily done through data collectives than by the individual acting alone:

2.2 Why are collectives more able to get value from data?

As identified in Section 1.1, one of the most common agendas for data collectives is the pursuit of data rights and empowerment issues. This can be done both from an Individualist (2.3.3) and 'Common Good' (2.3.2) perspective. This is where collectives can achieve the most socially impactful gain in extracting value from data - working towards the personal or social goals that individuals and groups of individuals can pursue through data.

Barriers to Individual Agency and Negotiability

As has been well established^{24,25}, and explored in more detail in the Digipower Technical Reports^{26,27}, there is a power imbalance between those who collect and use personal data and those individuals about whom the data is stored, with individuals having inadequate awareness, control and use of that data. People are routinely kept in the dark about what data exists about them, and the sacrifice of data that is needed to make use of digital services and consumer devices often acts as a *point of severance*²⁸, beyond which all control is lost, with organisations functioning as inaccessible *data traps*²⁹.

As such, individuals face many barriers to getting themselves into a position where they can use their data effectively:

1. *Awareness*: A lack of awareness of what data is held, and by whom;
2. *Access*: Hard-to-discover and hard-to-complete processes for accessing data³⁰;
3. *Sensemaking*: A lack of tools and technical skills to make sense of or make use of returned data;
4. *Integration*: A lack of tools and skills to unify and integrate scattered data from different sources in different formats;
5. *Agency & Negotiability*: No effective means to ask questions, object to inadequate responses or undesirable handling, and no way to compel providers to answer questions or change data handling practices;
6. *Context & Reflection*: A lack of reference information or wider context against which to judge their own data and its handling;

²⁴ World Economic Forum (2014), *Rethinking Personal Data Report Series*, <https://www.weforum.org/reports/rethinking-personal-data/>

²⁵ Zuboff, Shoshana (2019), *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*, Profile Books.

²⁶ Pidoux, Gursky, Bowyer, Dehaye (2022), *Digipower Technical Reports: Understanding Influence and Power in the Data Economy*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554155>

²⁷ Bowyer, Pidoux, Gursky, Dehaye (2022), *Digipower Technical Reports: Auditing the Data Economy through Personal Data Access*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554177>

²⁸ Luger, Ewa, and Tom Rodden (2013). *An informed view on consent for UbiComp*, Proceedings of the 2013 ACM international joint conference on Pervasive and ubiquitous computing.

²⁹ Abiteboul, Serge, Benjamin André, and Daniel Kaplan (2015), *Managing your digital life*, Communications of the ACM 58.5: 32-35.

³⁰ This has improved significantly since the introduction of GDPR in 2018, however despite easier capabilities such as download dashboards, individuals remain 'in the dark' and struggle to find value in their returned data - as described in Bowyer, Alex, et al. (2022) *Human-GDPR Interaction: Practical Experiences of Accessing Personal Data*, CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems.

7. *Involvement*: Even where data is obtained and understood, such processes are not integrated into normal data-centric processes that affect people's lives, and as such people lack a meaningful involvement in decision making.

Barriers such as these have been researched in detail. Recommended reading about these barriers includes:

- Li, Ian, Anind Dey, and Jodi Forlizzi (2010), *A stage-based model of personal informatics systems*, Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1753326.1753409>
- Gurstein, Michael B. (2011), *Open data: Empowering the empowered or effective data use for everyone?*, First Monday, 16(2), <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v16i2.3316>
- Mortier, Richard, et al. (2014), *Human-data interaction: The human face of the data-driven society*, Social Science Research Network, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2508051>
- Bowyer, Alex (2022), *Chapter 8: Mapping the Human Data Relations Landscape*, Understanding and Improving Human Data Relations, Thesis, Newcastle University.

In many cases, collectives form with a desire to tackle one or more of these barriers; for example, to help people get access to their data, to educate people about data, to provide tools to aid understanding, or to help represent individuals to digital service providers so that those individuals might be better involved in decisions that affect them.

How Collectives Can Help Challenge These Barriers

Here are 5 of the ways in which collectives may be able to help individuals overcome the above barriers and help people get value from data:

1. Getting better responses from companies with respect to data

In many cases, collectives are able to pressure companies or organisations to provide better responses to individuals, which can improve agency, negotiability, access and awareness. This can often come through using the influence of those in the collective. For example, journalists or high profile Internet personalities or whistleblowers can draw attention to inadequate transparency from companies, or in some cases use alternative

channels to get faster and better replies (such as journalists Mark Scott and Niclas Storas were able to do in the Digipower investigation). Also those individuals with influence on policy or links to regulators can also encourage companies to provide better responses - as seen with Filomena Chirico in the Digipower investigation. Even where there is not an influential person involved, collectives can mobilise large groups of individuals to all point their efforts and requests and responses in the same direction (see Section 3.2 for an example of this). Such actions can apply pressure to organisations to provide better responses, more than individuals can.

2. Applying “many eyes” (or “many brains”) to data understanding or accountability

Sensemaking, context gathering and reflection can all be improved when many people are involved in a collective looking at the same problem together. Individuals can *compare* their data, interface views and experiences interacting with organisations, to gain a *wider view* of how those organisations treat users as a whole, or how algorithms are treating different sections of the user base, or what inferences or categorisations exist for a user base. It stands to reason, especially given the highly personalised nature of data-driven web experiences today, that peoples’ data will differ vastly, and the more disparate datapoints can be gathered, the more accurate a bigger picture can be built up. Also, collectives offer the potential to share the work of analysing and interpreting data, for example by bringing in people with experience in data science or marketing to help interpret data, *pooling people’s skills*, so that people have access to capabilities they might not otherwise have, or simply by breaking down problems into smaller pieces that can be farmed out to individuals (see Section 3.5 for an example of this).

3. Providing tools to offer individuals new capabilities over data

Collectives can enhance individuals’ agency, especially when those collectives include software developers and data scientists, because tools and software can be built to offer individuals enhanced capabilities. For example, collective endeavours such as The Eyeballs (building a browser extension to reveal more of the adtech bidding constantly taking place online), noyb.eu (via their GDPR Hub³¹) and TapMyData (with request tools and a personal data store to hold received data)³², have offered tools and resources for helping people to access, managed and make sense of their personal data. Some of these collectives are more ‘involving’ and collaborative than others. TapMyData, for example, is shaped as a commercial service, whereas PersonalData.IO provides a

³¹ <https://noyb.eu/en/gdprhub>

³² <https://docs.tapmydata.com/our-technology/tapmydata-pds>

collective wiki space³³ where people can contribute their knowledge of different organisations' data formats and practices.

4. Educating people, improving skills and awareness

Collectives can improve people's awareness, sensemaking, and abilities to operate confidently and knowledgeably in the data-centric world, through educational efforts such as 1:1 coaching, workshops, or delivering training presentations and courses, or simply through the provision of online reference materials and knowledge hubs. For example, collectives can bring in experts to educate people on how to construct data access requests so as to be more effective, or on how to respond, or can show people and skill them up in accessing, interpreting and finding meaning and getting value from their own data.

5. 'Unionised' collective power

Increasingly, collectives are collaborating with worker unions and legal representatives, to learn how groups of users of services or platforms can come together and make use of data to help gather evidence and persuasive strategies to improve the ways that individuals are treated - this can include data-related topics such as improving transparency and accountability, but also social issues such as employee rights, fair marketplace conditions, or corporate social responsibilities. For examples of this kind of work, see Sections 3.3 and 3.4.

Other ways for collectives to get value from data

Before finishing this section, it is important also to address the third philosophy that collectives may follow - the capitalist approach (Section 2.3.1), where data is seen as a means to obtain value for businesses. In some cases, the ability of collectives to get more value from data is simply one of scale. This is often the case when companies or other organisations work together in a collective to improve their own data; simply by having access to more data about more people, provides a wider aggregate view, and with each participating organisation having different datapoints about an individual, the assembly of those different data points results in a more complete data record; this is the principle that many data brokers work upon. This sort of collective effort is explored further in Section 2.3.1 where capitalist collectives are described.

³³ https://wiki.personaldata.io/wiki/Main_Page

These advantages of scale for collective work are also available to organisations working together to pursue other philosophies - for example cooperatives working together with other cooperatives, or with open data sources - so this angle on the collective / aggregate view of data should not be viewed only from a capitalist frame.

2.3 Three Philosophies for Collectives

When individuals or organisations come together around data, there is always a greater purpose to the endeavour. All collectives are created to serve a particular agenda or master, and drive towards a particular goal. Being clear about that purpose is helpful for understanding why the collective exists, and what constitutes success for that collective. Certainly, for data collectives, there is a desire to produce or harness knowledge in order to effect change.

We can identify three major philosophies which motivate collectives: **Capitalism**, **The Common Good**, and **Individualism**. If this sounds overly theoretical, consider this: Data collectives can be seen as engine for knowledge. But who is the beneficiary/intended owner of the knowledge? Who are they collecting knowledge for and who do they confer benefit upon? Does the collective effort hope to further a business goal, help society at large, or to empower individuals?

It is possible for collectives to draw from multiple philosophies, but in practice we find most collectives are well situated within one of these three philosophies:

Capitalist Collectives

One motivation for data collectives that is not often considered, is the capitalist one. That is, when organisations, in pursuit of profit (typically through the improving of customer profiling and targeting, attribution of ad conversions, etc.), attempt to share data (or more often to “compute together” in a *data clean room*^{34,35} which avoids direct, individual-level data sharing or exfiltration) in order to learn from what each other knows about each customer.

³⁴ <https://liveramp.com/blog/data-clean-room/>

³⁵ <https://infotrust.com/articles/data-clean-room-ads-data-hub/>

For example, from 2018-2021 Adobe ran a programme called Experience Cloud Device Co-op³⁶, which allowed companies and brands to connect together personal data about which devices an individual is using to access those companies' services. Through sharing and pooling data, the brands working together were able to build up pictures of which devices a given customer is using, and indeed of the different members of a customer's household that might be targeted.

In another example, Google and Mastercard developed a complicated collective effort, using double blind encryption, to allow them to match physical purchases with credit cards, to Google ads³⁷. Through analysis of pooled hashed data from both sources they were able to anonymously match up physical store purchases with clicked online Google ads, providing valuable feedback on ad targeting effectiveness. A similar approach was observed between Finnish retailer Gigantti with Facebook and Google during the Digipower investigation, as detailed in the technical reports³⁸.

Much of the collaborative work between companies in today's data-centric world could be viewed through the collective lens. This is often seen in the sharing and unification of data within corporations that own data about customers through their different sub brands or constituent companies. Indeed the entire data broker industry is a macrocosm of data-sharing collectives. However for the purposes of this definition we are more interested in the more narrowly focused efforts where companies specifically work with partners to unify customer data for their collective benefit.

Capitalist collectives are, by default, not interested in improving individuals' lives or helping society - only in understanding people better through data so that this understanding can support a better commercial service, including in its marketing.

'Common Good' Collectives

'Common Good' collectives have existed for a long time outside the world of data; these are simply grassroots groups, cooperatives or campaigns that aim to further some social cause that benefits everyone and makes a better environment or society for all: for example Amnesty International, Greenpeace, the Electoral Reform Society, or Keep

³⁶

<https://news.adobe.com/news/news-details/2018/Adobe-Launches-Experience-Cloud-Device-Co-op/default.aspx>

³⁷ <https://archive.ph/SLmFw>

³⁸ Bowyer, Pidoux, Gursky, Dehaye (2022), *Digipower Technical Reports: Auditing the Data Economy through Personal Data Access*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554177>

Britain Tidy. “The Common Good” is an established school of philosophical, political and economic thought^{39,40}.

Following the emergence of e-commerce and digital society, we now see many collectives moving in the direction of pursuing societal goals through becoming a data collective, or pursuing societal goals that specifically relate to data.

As an example, in the UK an organisation called TheyWorkForYou⁴¹ aims to improve democracy through the creation of easy-to-understand and search summaries of what votes have happened in the UK Parliament, and what particular MPs have voted for. While they do not collect personal data, they clearly unlock the value of otherwise hard-to-access-and-understand data, in pursuit of the societal goal of a more functional democracy.

Another example of collectives sharing data for social good is the Feed Finder app⁴², developed at Open Lab at Newcastle University in the UK. Through the creation of a software app and service that allows people to contribute geo-tagged reviews, this allows breastfeeding mothers to share information about their experiences of breastfeeding in different public places. This provides a social benefit of making it easier to find breastfeeding-friendly places, but also could have a social impact by pressuring venue owners to respond to poor reviews, much like a bad TripAdvisor Review. The challenges and impacts of such an initiative are explored further in research papers⁴³. The app went on to create a platform that enables other communities to form and create their own similar apps for other uses as diverse as drone flying and improving air quality⁴⁴.

Another example arising in the research community, also at Open Lab, was that of Spokespeople⁴⁵. This collective was designed to allow cyclists to collect a pool of data about dangerous cycle lanes, potholes, or other public road infrastructure which was problematic or unsafe to cyclists, so that the data could be pooled and presented to local councils as evidence to convince them to invest in road repairs or improved cycling infrastructure to benefit all. This worked through a simple Bluetooth button that cyclists

³⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_good

⁴⁰ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/common-good/>

⁴¹ <https://www.theyworkforyou.com/>

⁴² <https://openlab.ncl.ac.uk/research/feedfinder-app-tripadvisor-for-breastfeeding/>

⁴³ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3025453.3025881>

⁴⁴ <https://app-movement.com/discover>

⁴⁵ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3173574.3173979>

could attach to their handlebars, linked to a mobile phone app that centrally collected the data. The system did not fully roll out as an ongoing collective, but serves as a powerful example of how people can come together through data to pursue a social common good.

‘Common Good’ collectives can be distinguished from capitalist collectives in that they aim to further societal or environmental causes rather than a particular corporation’s objectives, and from individualist collectives in that they focus more on creating a fairer/better/more equitable world for everyone, rather than focusing on what individuals can or cannot do; in other words, focusing on the status quo or environment rather than the individual.

Individualist Collectives

Individualism (again an established school of philosophical thought⁴⁶) concerns the premise that the most important thing is to ensure that individuals are free to better themselves and pursue their own goals, free from imposition or interference from the state or from corporate actors. In the current global context, this largely manifests as actions designed to fight against the prevailing practices of surveillance capitalism and algorithmic decision-making, although can also be framed more positively, through collective actions that aim to create new technologies that give people new capabilities or express themselves in new ways, such as in the maker movement.

As with ‘social good’ collectives, individualist collective action is not new, and can exist without a focus on the topic of data or upon the use of data. One example of a social collective that is starting to get more focused on data is the Open Rights Group, in the UK. This is a grassroots organisation focused on protecting privacy and threats to free speech⁴⁷ - in line with the individualist philosophy of removing impositions upon individuals by the state or by powerful actors. A recent campaign by the organisation that was more focused on data was when they invited members of the group to submit GDPR requests and share the data returned⁴⁸. By looking at these responses collectively, they were able to draw conclusions about how political parties see citizens through data, which informs their campaigns for individual privacy and fair representation.

⁴⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Individualism>

⁴⁷ <https://www.openrightsgroup.org/who-we-are/>

⁴⁸

<https://www.openrightsgroup.org/blog/what-weve-learned-from-asking-political-parties-who-do-you-think-we-are/>

Another example, which highlights the key collective practice of *data donation*, is youchoose.ai. This non-profit group aims to tackle the injustices against people through algorithmic influences (both indirectly, through personalised recommendations and directly, through algorithmic decisions)⁴⁹. They invite users to donate their youtube recommendations history, and educate users about the impacts of algorithmic recommendations. Both of these functions are offered through a web browser extension; a piece of software that modifies the appearance and functionality of a website after it has been loaded into a user's browser⁵⁰. The data that users have donated can then be analysed to reverse engineer YouTube's algorithm, for example uncovering so-called 'shadow bans' where a creator's videos are silently hidden. A similar approach (using web browsers to collect users' data which is then analysed centrally to improve accountability and scrutiny) is seen in WhoTargetsMe, which is described in Section 3.1.

A final example seen in individualist collectives that is worth mentioning is the phenomenon of Adversarial Interoperability⁵¹, sometimes known as Civic Hacking or seam hacking⁵². Here, individuals get together to find ways to exploit opportunities in the edges of products and platforms - for example using web scraping or reverse engineering of internal APIs, to access data that is not readily available to users or expose functionality and connect products in ways that the manufacturers did not intend. This is an ongoing battleground, where law tends to favour the manufacturer or platform provider's right to restrict what users can do, but users' sense of rights to use their own data and products in the ways they see fit, give the individualist & adversarial interoperability approach a moral grounding as "a fair and reasonable thing to do". This closely connects with the Right to Repair movement, and more recently the Right to Fair Programs⁵³. The collective aspects here often revolve around the sharing of information around known workarounds and exploits, and the education of end users to acquire new access and capabilities, or the provision of software tools to achieve the same.

Individualist collectives can be distinguished from "common good" collectives by their focus on attempting to improve what one individual can do by him/herself, rather than a focus on global environmental factors or systemic injustice. Like "common good"

⁴⁹ <https://youchoose.ai/philosophy>

⁵⁰ <https://youchoose.ai/addon>

⁵¹ <https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2019/10/adversarial-interoperability>

⁵² <https://doi.org/10.1145/2661435.2661436>

⁵³ "I want my app that way: Reclaiming Sovereignty over Digital Devices", Konrad Kollnig et al., <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3411763.3451632>

collectives, individualist collectives differ from capitalist collectives in that they measure value in human terms such as agency, freedom and autonomy rather than business success or profit.

2.4 Three Paradigms of Collective Work

Having considered what motivates collectives in the previous section, we can now consider what sort of activities a collective may *do*, in pursuit of those goals.

The activities carried out within a collective typically fall into one of the following three types. A collective may carry out activities of one, two or all three types.

Investigative

Investigative activity focuses upon **accumulating** new knowledge, and sharing and interpreting it for collective benefit. This knowledge will typically be knowledge obtained through acquiring, pooling and analysing or comparing data from different individuals. The knowledge in question may also include knowledge inferred about how to access data, or about how particular data holders use data, or their processes.

Some of the example activities that could count as investigative are:

- Carrying out GDPR access requests to obtain data from companies, to extract value from that data for members, or to learn about the data holder and their practices;
- Using other GDPR rights such as rights to explanation and to be informed, asking specific questions about provider practices, decision making, or inferences;
- Using auditing techniques such as Tracker Control⁵⁴ / iOS App Activity Report to identify third parties with which a company might be sharing data. Identified third parties can then be targeted further with GDPR;
- Traditional investigative journalism techniques;
- Interviewing;
- Expert data analysis;
- Production of aggregate statistics to highlight concerning aspects or practices;
- Comparison of data points between individuals, to identify categorisations, possible field choice values, biases, different user segment treatments etc;
- Building up a pool of data or knowledge as evidence or reference information;

⁵⁴ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=net.kollnig.missioncontrol.play>

- Reverse engineering applications to see how they are using data or how they are connecting to third party services;
- Carrying out participatory research to explore how people view data, what they can learn through data access requests about data holders, or how they respond to new models of data interaction such as personal data lockers.

A common goal of investigative techniques is to uncover hidden/unknown practices, or to hold data holders to account against what they say in privacy policies or what the law says they should do.

It is important to highlight that there are two distinct types of knowledge sought:

- Information *about the data subject* (i.e. what does the data say about them) - sometimes called *life information*;
- Information *about the subject's data ecosystem* (e.g. what is happening to the subjects data, where is it stored, who is it being shared with, what are different entities doing with it) - sometimes called *data ecosystem information*

The concepts of life information and data ecosystem information are explained in Alex Bowyer's thesis where they are explored further.

Investigative efforts can be helped by sharing the workload of investigation among members of a collective. See Sections 3.1 and 3.5 for more examples of this.

Educational

Education activity focuses outward, **spreading** the collective's knowledge to increase the awareness and skills of others in the general public. Often that increased awareness will focus on improving data ecosystem awareness (and hence, the accountability of data holders), or of improving people's understanding of their data or ability to use it.

Some of the example activities that could count as educational are:

- Running a workshop;
- Producing a website with self guided flows or forms to automate tasks such as asserting one's data rights or making a GDPR request;
- Running clinics where people can get help with data-related questions;
- Visiting a school and teaching schoolchildren about data-related issues;
- Creating self-help or online training materials;

- Creating knowledge repositories about companies and data (e.g. GDPRHub⁵⁵, PersonalData.io Wiki⁵⁶);
- Producing interactive tools that visualise and explain personal data (e.g. Digipower Academy⁵⁷, exist.io⁵⁸);
- Creating initiatives that have the potential to convert interested members of the public into scientists and researchers - such as OpenHumans.org, or Zooniverse (see 3.5);
- Training journalists on the techniques of data access and collective data examination as an investigative process; or
- Running 1:1 'explore your data' coaching sessions (such as in Digipower project)

Central to educational endeavours of collectives is that the members of the collective must first gain knowledge and expertise, and then develop ways to surface that expertise and knowledge in relatable ways - be that through the presentation of information in person or the creation of online self-service tools. Digipower.academy is an example of the educational work that a collective can produce, as it offers both in-person training and courses as well as online-self help tools where you can upload your own data and be presented with easy-to-understand and explore visualisations.

Activist

Activist activities focus on **leveraging** the collective's knowledge, influence or resources outwards on pressuring data holders to change, or attempting to change societal norms in people's data-related behaviours. The desired changes often relate to increased individual agency, increased transparency and accountability of powerful data holders or state actors, or attempts to shift user demand, brand loyalty, etc. away from services that are deemed problematic, towards more favourable ones.

The idea of an activist collective can be seen to draw from the idea of a 'recursive public', a collective that aims to reconfigure itself and its society in order to pursue its goals. This idea has roots in the free software movement, and has been defined as 'a

⁵⁵ <https://noyb.eu/en/gdprhub>

⁵⁶ https://wiki.personaldata.io/wiki/Main_Page

⁵⁷ <https://digipower.academy/>

⁵⁸ <https://exist.io/>

collective, independent of other forms of constituted power, capable of speaking to existing forms of power through the production of actually existing alternatives⁵⁹.

This objective (and the ability to pursue it) becomes important in situations where individuals have very little collective governance - those where their ability to collectively communicate and act is limited - like the Farmville scenario described in the Digipower Technical Reports⁶⁰. Facebook users, for example, cannot leave the platform even when they feel it harms them. As Cory Doctorow put it:

“[Facebook users wanting to leave] had a *collective action* problem. Each of them could figure out what worked best for them, but getting together to decide what was best for all of them was literally impossible.”⁶¹

Some of the example activities that a collective could do that are more activist in nature include:

- Mobilising large numbers of people to contact, make demands of, or boycott particular brands, services or companies;
- Mobilising large numbers of people to use data rights against specific target organisations, resulting in a collective pressure;
- Uniting employees or users of a service around a common cause and demanding changes in a union-style manner;
- Transferring control of acquired, pooled or inferred data, tools and resources to communities, user groups or individuals;
- Providing templates, forms and simple button-click interfaces to make it easy for individuals to exert their rights (e.g. make a data request, email your MP);
- Petitions and protests;
- Impact journalism, exposing/shaming company bad practices;
- Ethical hacking / Seam Hacking / Adversarial Interoperability - pushing the boundaries of the ways in which products can be used, through the release of plugins, adaptors, exploits, workarounds, scripts, software, or instructions, enabling people to gain new capabilities over data or access otherwise inaccessible data or functionality;

⁵⁹ https://wiki.p2pfoundation.net/Recursive_Public (wikipedia including extracts from the book “Two Bits: The Cultural Significance of Free Software” by Christopher Kelty (2008))

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554155>

⁶¹ <https://doctorow.medium.com/how-to-leave-dying-social-media-platforms-9fc550fe5abf>

- Legal actions, class action lawsuits, complaints to regulators - drawing the attention of authorities to perceived wrongdoing so that law may be better enforced (see e.g. 3.2);
- Modification of user interfaces through web augmentation / web extensions and other techniques;

Many of these can be classified as *collective action*. In general, collectives can have more impact than individuals, in part simply through their greater numbers, but also through carefully targeted actions optimised to motivate others to act or change.

3. The Impacts of Data Collectives

In the previous section, we explained how collectives operate and what motivates them. In this section, we look at the impacts that a successful data collective can have upon society and what value it can offer to its contributors and members. The world of collectives is complex and full of opportunities to improve society. Introducing a data collective into this ecosystem can be an effective way to understand the stakes of a certain issue and to influence thinking and behaviours. Data collectives can stimulate individuals and organisations, constructively interfere in their established reasoning and operating models, and awaken their awareness of the personal data economy. To illustrate this, we highlight the work done by a few example collectives. This shows, exemplified by real world stories, impacts that collectives can have, while also looking at how those collectives are structured, so that we may gain insights that can be applied to other data collectives.

3.1 WhoTargetsMe: Pursuing Algorithmic Accountability

Collective	WhoTargetsMe ⁶² (and similar initiatives ^{63,64,65})
Philosophy	Common Good
Paradigm	Investigative (+ Educational)

⁶² <https://whotargets.me/en/about-who-targets-me/>

⁶³ <https://www.allsides.com/about>

⁶⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa1160>

⁶⁵ <https://adobservatory.org/>

Summary Description	<p>An activist research project, which enables the monitoring and scrutiny of online political ads and personalised microtargeting. Volunteers install a web browser extension which gathers data about ads served while the user browses social media. This data is centrally collected and analysed to identify ad spending in real time. Given that everyone's feed is different, this enables scrutiny of what would otherwise not be transparent. They also have other projects and services including consulting, open data access, proposals for standard political ad data formats, maps and trends visualisers.</p>
Its Members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The founders / lead researchers, who created and operate the project ● Funding bodies, research agencies and individual donors, ● Over 50,000 volunteers who have installed the web browser plugin and collected data about the ads they have seen ● Research partners, who have collaborated on analysis and scientific and journalistic publications based on the data
Interface(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The WhoTargetsMe web browser extension, for Chrome Safari, Edge and Firefox, which allows data collection ● The WhoTargetsMe blog⁶⁶, where findings (from over 10 elections worldwide, and intervening periods) are disseminated to the public ● The WhoTargetsMe website, where data access, code access, and information and visualisations from the project are available ● The results website⁶⁷, where anyone can look up data and visualisations on ad spending by party for particular constituencies , demographics, etc.
Protocol(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extension Installation ● Data Access ● Viewing Results and Findings ● Donating to support the project ● Receiving news and updates from the project
Contribution(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data (contributed through the browser)

⁶⁶ <https://medium.com/@WhoTargetsMe>

⁶⁷ <https://results.whotargets.me/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Funding (grants and individual donations)
Returns:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased understanding of how political advertisers are spending their ad dollars and who they are targeting ● Repository of data about ads shown to users to support future research and analysis ● Scientific and journalistic publication of findings

In 2017, activists Sam Jeffers and Louis Knight Webb founded WhoTargetsMe, with the goal of gathering data to hold political advertisers (and social media platforms) to account. By creating a web extension, they enabled thousands of people to act as “many eyeballs” over the disparate personalised information landscapes (as described in the Digipower Technical report on influence and power⁶⁸), sharing their data into a collective pool for analysis. They then made this data available to the public, and other researchers, and continue to offer interpretations, findings and insights via their blogs^{69,70}, allowing citizens of over 100 countries to see how they are being targeted, and how their political parties are spending money on social media advertising.

Note that the contributors have little involvement in the decisions taken with their data, and that one of the main processes here is actually to anonymize the personal data as soon as possible in order to enable further downstream activities.

Further reading: NYTimes⁷¹, The Guardian⁷²

3.2 Max Schrems v Facebook: Improved Individual Rights

In 2017 data protection activist Max Schrems founded a nonprofit called NOYB, following earlier successful efforts of data-driven lobbying and litigation. While the earlier ventures were collective efforts aimed at empowering individuals to file complaints and contribute to broader legal actions (partly through technical automation in order to enlist many participants), following the establishment of NOYB these operations have professionalised and now mostly use NOYB staff acting through their

⁶⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554155>

⁶⁹ <https://whotargets.me/en/blog/>

⁷⁰ <https://medium.com/@whotargetsme>

⁷¹ <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/06/07/technology/facebook-britain-election-europe.html>

⁷²

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2019/nov/09/facebook-voters-used-as-lab-rats-targeted-political-advertising>

own data as plaintiffs. The outside appeal is now towards fundraising rather than being data driven, at least for now.

Collective	'Europe versus Facebook' / noyb ("None of Your Business") / European Centre for Data Rights, and Max Schrems' other ventures
Philosophy	Individualist
Paradigm	Activist (+ Investigative, Educational)
Summary Description	<p>From 2011 onwards, Austrian lawyer and privacy activist Max Schrems has taken many actions against Facebook, and on behalf of its users, in pursuit of better data access. While some of these actions were individual, many involved harnessed collectives of people to achieve results.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2011, he created the "Europe v Facebook" a website that helped over 40,000 people generate data access requests to Facebook, as a result of which Facebook created their self-service "Download Your Information" website so that they could avoid handling these requests. • In 2014, he formed a class action lawsuit of over 25,000 people in the Austrian courts for alleged illegal tracking of users' data (which was ultimately not allowed to proceed). • In 2017, he founded the non-profit noyb organisation focused on enforcing privacy rights in Europe, which offered paid membership to fund its operations.
Its Members	<p>Europe v Facebook users (~40,000 people): individuals who used the website to make GDPR requests to Facebook</p> <p>2014 lawsuit applicants (~25,000 people): individuals who signed up to participate in the 2014 lawsuit and request compensation.</p> <p>2014 lawsuit interested parties (number unknown): individuals who registered an interest in the 2014 lawsuit without requesting compensation (exists due to 25,000 person limit).</p> <p>Noyb donors/members: (over €460,000 donated) individuals who donated financially to the foundation of the non-profit noyb organisation.</p> <p>Noyb / ECDR representatives (~30 people) : Staff, Voting</p>

	Members, and Executive Board of the Austrian non-profit organisation.
Interface(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The fbclaim website⁷³, which allowed individuals to sign up to join the class action (or later, to register an interest⁷⁴) • The Europe v Facebook “Get Your Data” website (and its other information sections)⁷⁵ • The noyb informational and members’ website⁷⁶. • The GDPRhub wiki⁷⁷, listing different jurisprudence cases relating to GDPR enforcement.
Protocol(s):	<p>Crowdfunding: where donations are made by individuals or organisations to help fund not-for-profit work to further the cause of enforcing individual data access rights</p> <p>Web Forms: where websites with well-defined workflows are created to funnel interested but non-expert individuals into pre-existing channels (such as to contact Facebook’s Data Protection Officer)</p> <p>GDPR Representation: where noyb as an organisation acts on individuals’ behalf (using Article 20 of the GDPR) to pursue data access requests on their behalf.</p> <p>Legal Actions: where Schrems and colleagues took legal cases to various European courts to defend individual rights.</p> <p>Public Information: where information about the various court cases and campaigns are communicated back to the public through websites and social media</p> <p>Journalistic Engagements: Where information is shared, and attention gained, through engagement with journalists in the form of press releases, interviews, blogs and social media etc.</p>
Contribution(s):	<p>Financial: Where money is provided through donation or funding grants etc.</p> <p>Adding Oneself to a Pool: Where value is added through adding more people to the pool of people.</p> <p>Learning through the sum of individual actions: Encouraging many people to perform similar actions (such as a data access</p>

⁷³ <https://web.archive.org/web/20140801183658/https://www.fbclaim.com/ui/signin>

⁷⁴ <https://web.archive.org/web/20140811023751/https://www.fbclaim.com/ui/register>

⁷⁵ <http://www.europe-v-facebook.org/EN/en.html>

⁷⁶ <https://noyb.eu/en>

⁷⁷ <https://gdprhub.eu/>

	request), and recontextualizing the results for their own lives. Documenting GDPR enforcement cases.
Returns:	<p>Individual Utility: achieving some individual result, such as getting data you couldn't otherwise get</p> <p>New Tools: the creation of new tools, especially if offered by providers, such as Facebook's download tool</p> <p>Provider Behaviour Change: Changes in provider behaviour, such as providing better responses to future data access requests from individuals</p> <p>Legal & Regulatory Impact: Such as fines on data holding companies, or mandated actions by courts, or assistance to other NGOs or legal experts through their wiki/knowledge base.</p> <p>Learning together: Through a collective process, participants can learn of practices of companies.</p>

NOYB and Schrems are well-established players, so we will not dwell too much on them. We will however highlight an evolution over time of Schrems' approach. While at first he was trying to encourage many people to exercise their rights or to join him as citizens - all the while acting as a role model, NOYB has professionalised his action and has allowed him to scale it up. One key remarkable element is that the data subjects requesting their data or executing procedures are now employees or interns of NOYB, thereby reinforcing the view of NOYB itself as a data collective.

3.3 Uber Drivers: From fairer working conditions to rethinking mobility

We want here to describe ongoing work in Geneva around the initiation of a data collective of Uber drivers. This work has gathered many actors, with differing motives, but was spurred around labour issues for Uber drivers. It is explicitly and intentionally shifting in focus over time, going from labour issues to a rethinking of the role of data in building mobility solutions, and then further extending onto thinking about new business models around data.

In order to understand this example, one needs to understand the general context in which it is being started, and hence the external pressures and intrinsic motivations:

- a June 2022 judgement of the Swiss highest court has confirmed a 2019 labour court judgement that the individual Uber driver who had initially complained was

- actually an employee - with a retrospective impact on their pay (minimal hourly salary, car expenses, etc);
- since each individual driver would still have to go to labour court to get their rights similarly respected, the immediate consequence of this judgement is only that they would have an easier time defending their case;
 - the Geneva canton has decided to ban Uber operating a transport service in Geneva for as long as they don't comply with their newly confirmed labour obligations⁷⁸;
 - in exchange for an immediate suspension of this interdiction, Uber has agreed to setting up of an accelerated compensation procedure which drivers could opt in, instead of going to labour court;
 - the lynchpin of such a procedure would be in the basic formula to use to quickly establish the compensation owed to each driver;
 - labour unions and driver representatives were invited to the Summer 2022 negotiation around this formula, which hinged partly on which variables to actually use as input for a formula to then apply to each driver's individual circumstances (labour unions for instance insisted that time spent in the car without passenger should still count towards work hours);
 - Geneva-based parties to this negotiation requested multiple time access to aggregate statistics and (consenting) individual driver raw data, for which Uber was less than forthcoming;
 - the negotiation failed, but eventually the Canton agreed to a facilitated reimbursement procedure proposed by Uber based exclusively on kilometres driven with a passenger on board;
 - labour unions and many driver representatives disagree on the deal, and keep on pointing at variables kept obscure through that formula (for instance: hours spent waiting without a passenger, kilometres driven empty).

As of end 2022, each driver is left with a personal choice between two options:

- accept a facilitated compensation procedure not taking into account much of their own individual circumstance, and most likely underpaying them;
- go to labour court and argue for their individual case.

⁷⁸ Note that the labour judgement is at federal level: technically, it applies to other cantons as well, who differentiate their circumstances by arguing that their own local transportation laws do not allow similarly pinning the authorization to operate a local transport company to respect federal labour laws.

Following legal proceedings concerning Uber and its drivers, Hestia has built tools to visualise the data that Uber collects on its drivers. All this in order to help drivers to better understand the situation and thus enable the driver to judge whether the proposals made by Uber are fair to them or not. It is then possible to see this whole organisation as a data collective. As a result, several actors and stakeholders in the legal process, such as lawyers or labour unions, have become interested in Hestia's tools.

This conflict shows the state of things in the digital world. That is to say, where the use of data generated by users are only exploited for commercial purposes. All this is done in an economic-centric way without asking the users' opinion. But as said above the data is generated by the users and so if there is no user there is no data. So users have a big role to play in this data industry. The goal of this data collective and maybe in a more general way, is to put the users back at the centre of the debate and this necessarily passes by a reappropriation of the personal data and of the knowledge of the treatments of these.

This collective can be described as a data collective because its main resource is the drivers' data and then the collective organises itself to give value to the data. Hestia does this by allowing the data to be visualised with their tools as well as by making time available (e.g., for permanences) to the drivers or lawyers to explain the procedures, graphs, etc. Lawyers also do this by using the knowledge they have gained by participating in the collective in their defence case in the legal process.

The labour unions are also interested in what is going on around this collective data and may soon be able to be part of it as well if they deem it useful and if the drivers deem it useful to their cause.

There is additionally the intention of expanding focus from labour issues towards the secondary use of this data towards questions of mobility. In a sense, this is further along in Paris with the worker collective MazeCab⁷⁹, which is starting to work with regional authorities around Paris towards such secondary uses.

Here is a brief description of the collective.

⁷⁹ <https://www.maze.cab/>

Data Collective	Uber driver
Philosophy	Individualist (+ Common Good)
Paradigm	Activist
Summary description	In June 2019 the Uber-Geneva drivers wanted to be recognized as employees by Uber, so they filed a lawsuit against Uber. The Swiss federal court ruled in favour of the drivers. Thus Uber owes the drivers arrears for the period 2019-2022, the amount of arrears is the main issue in the procedure. Uber has made a proposal to the drivers, so it remains for the drivers to decide what they want to do. Drivers find it hard to prove exactly what hours they have driven, and that data can help with that, but only through the collective and Hestia help are they able to make use of / understand / gather evidence from the data.
Its Members	Uber drivers, Hestia(At the moment), PersonalData.io
Interfaces	<p>Digipower academy's website: where the data can be seen through the experiences and where the instructions about data requests are written.</p> <p>Chat group (Telegram, Whatsapp, Discord, ...): where employees of Hestia.ai inform and advise drivers on future events or procedures.</p> <p>Permanences : place where employees of Hestia.ai come together and do the same thing as in the chat groups but face to face. They also show to the drivers the digipower academy's website and run the experiences with their (drivers) own personal data. It is an accompaniment, a collaboration between hestia's employees and drivers. But the goal is that the drivers make it individually.</p>
Protocols	<p>Permanences : the procedure of how to organise a permanence.</p> <p>Data request : the process of how to conduct the legal procedure for requesting access to personal data.</p>

Contributions	For the driver : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time ● Their data For Hestia : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time ● Software ● Tools ● Consulting
Returns	For the driver : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More knowledge about the power of their data. ● Accounting mockup: excel sheet that shows the number of runs made, the number of hours in a state (waiting, approaching or running) and other more subtle data useful to their case. This table is also useful for lawyers who can use it as a resource and support in the defence of the case. For Hestia : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reputation ● Expertise

The logic of building this collective should be a common thread for future data collectives. That is, firstly there is a need for platform's users to be better represented in terms of the data they generate whether it is in order to have better working conditions, better treatments, to have more weight in the debate or simply for more transparency regarding data flows. Secondly, to better understand the data that platforms have on them, they need support (time, tool, software, advice) from experts in the field. Then, "secondary" actors can be added to the collective and this can be done for different purposes/motivations but always in agreement with the users because, let's remember, the aim is to put the people at the centre of the debate around data. For now the secondary actors come mainly from the world of advertising but fortunately there are projects that go in different directions such as the POSMO⁸⁰ project or FairTube⁸¹.

The POSMO project intends to show that large quantities of personal data can be managed for the common good. The team has created an ethical and transparent data cooperative to collect and manage mobility data on a central platform. Every individual

⁸⁰ <https://www.migros-engagement.ch/en/news-projects/technology-ethics/posmo>

⁸¹ <https://fairtube.info/en/>

feeding data into the platform can become a member of the cooperative, and participate in decisions as to what happens to the data. Enabled by the Migros Pioneer Fund, POSMO is undergoing a year-long pilot phase to validate the project, carry out initial market testing, and test technical feasibility.

The notion of worker collective is not limited to mobility workers. For instance, FairTube stands for fairness, transparency, accountability, dialogue, freedom from discrimination, and democratic participation for all platform creators and workers. Their goal is to ensure fair working conditions for all online workers worldwide. We can see similar dynamics there, where these platform workers have started working with AG Metall, one of the largest labour union in Germany.

3.4 MIDATA and other Health Data Coops

Data Collective	MIDATA ⁸²
Philosophy	Common Good + Individualist
Paradigm	Investigative
Summary description	MIDATA Cooperative is a nonprofit cooperative, and personal data platform, founded in 2015. It allows individuals to upload their health data and authorise the use of that data in research projects. Optionally those individuals may also get to use smartphone apps built using data and services from the platform, to gain health insights. The platform offers the ability for new cooperatives and science projects to form, and acts as a data trust, keeping data safe and handling consent of data subjects. A key focus is on individuals maintaining control over their health data.

⁸² <https://www.midata.coop/en/cooperative/>

Its Members	<p>Data account holders - individual citizens who upload their health data into the platform's data stores, optionally making it available for use by MIDATA Projects</p> <p>Members - financial contributors to the Cooperative, who have democratic rights to govern the running of the organisation (may or may not also be data account holders)</p> <p>MIDATA Project Operators - teams of scientists or health professionals who run projects on the MIDATA platform, using donated data</p> <p>Research Partners - other scientists or research institutes involved in conducting research based upon or related to MIDATA and its projects,</p> <p>MIDATA Organisation Staff (including operations team, ethics council, board of directors)</p> <p>Smartphone app users - users of apps that offer functionality based upon the MIDATA platform data and services - these individuals may or may not also be data account holders (ie. they may get benefits related to their own data, or to the aggregate data of others)</p>
Interfaces	<p>Specific projects or health data cooperatives hosted on the platform, such as CoronaScience⁸³, AllyScience⁸⁴, SFKMindcare⁸⁵</p> <p>MIDATA platform APIs to store and retrieve data</p> <p>Third party apps that use the platform's APIs</p> <p>The MIDATA website⁸⁶ for general information, donations, contacts, etc</p>
Protocols	<p>Create project</p> <p>Upload data to project</p> <p>Join Coop (paying Member Fee)</p> <p>Build app using MIDATA API</p> <p>Download & use app that uses MIDATA platform</p>

⁸³ <https://coronascience.ch/de/>

⁸⁴ <https://allyscience.ch/en/home/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.midata.coop/en/offer/sfk-mindcare/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.midata.coop/en/home/>

Contributions	Own Health Data Money Project Specs & Designs Application Code Voting/democratic decision making over running of coop
Returns	Insights on your personal health data Insights from aggregate data analysis & research Apps offering new functionalities/features Ability to collaborate with others in a community (For researchers) access to a pool of data and volunteers Contribution to Science/Research/Human Knowledge

MIDATA coop has similarities to other platforms that enable people to licence their health (or other) data for use in research, including saluscoop⁸⁷, OpenHumans⁸⁸ and digi.me⁸⁹/UBDI⁹⁰. In its ability for individuals and groups to set up their own projects, it also has similarities with citizen science projects such as The Zooniverse (see next section, 3.5).

3.5 Citizen Science and the Zooniverse

Collective	The Zooniverse
Philosophy	Common Good
Paradigm(s)	Investigative
Summary Description	A citizen science platform where scientists can make use of human brain power to refine and annotate data. Volunteers look at images and other media and use their judgement to identify patterns and classify information - e.g. species identification, transcription, and labelling.

⁸⁷ <https://www.saluscoop.org/acerca>

⁸⁸ <https://www.openhumans.org/>

⁸⁹ <https://digi.me/>

⁹⁰ <https://twitter.com/UBDIapp>

Its Members	<p>Volunteers: Who complete workflows of tasks to classify and respond to data</p> <p>Project Creators: Who design workflows of tasks for volunteers to complete</p> <p>Scientists: Who submit raw data and receive aggregate results which they analyse</p> <p>Community Moderators: Who help volunteers with issues and questions, and help grow communities around each project</p> <p>The Zooniverse host institutions: who provide software, hosting and expertise to run the platform</p>
Interface(s)	<p>Projects Catalogue - where people can find a project to volunteer for</p> <p>Classification Interface - where volunteers work on classifying data</p> <p>Project Builder - where workflows and tasks can be created and designed</p> <p>Data Exports Interface - where scientists can download classified data from their project</p> <p>Community Forums - where all members can discuss and communicate about the projects and tasks</p> <p>Zooniverse website - containing more information about the projects, publications, people and other news.</p>
Protocol(s):	<p>Project design & data uploading: where researchers create tasks and workflows and populate them with raw unclassified data</p> <p>Data classification: Where volunteers examine data through workflows and classify data</p> <p>Data export: where scientists extract results data</p> <p>Community participation: Where all parties discuss and collaborate around the projects and tasks</p> <p>Project promotion: Where projects can request to be featured on the project catalogue, and will be reviewed by a panel to verify standards are met and whether or not the project will be promoted</p> <p>Bespoke services: Where research organisations can pay for additional bespoke features, support and services.</p>
Contribution(s):	<p>Time/Brainpower: Volunteers and moderators donate their time and brainpower</p> <p>Money & Staffing: Zooniverse host institutions invest financially</p>

	<p>in technology stacks and human resources including software developers.</p> <p>Raw Data: Scientists/researchers contribute raw datasets that need human classification</p> <p>Additional Funding: in some cases, research organisations contribute financially to the platform in return for bespoke project development and support</p>
Returns:	<p>Classified Data: which researchers receive once their projects have been partly or fully classified by volunteers.</p> <p>Enjoyment and Reward: volunteers enjoy the classification and find reward in knowing they are helping to advance science</p> <p>Contributions to Science, and Society: the classified data from Zooniverse projects is analysed and used in research, which often leads to publications which can have social benefits, increasing mankind’s understanding of history, climate, literature, medicine, science, arts and the natural world. Zooniverse projects have resulted in hundreds of published papers, and novel discoveries such as a new type of astronomical phenomenon.</p> <p>Formation of Communities: through coming together around data and tasks, new communities of enthusiastic volunteers have formed. The Zooniverse community at large is huge, with over a million people having participated.</p>

The Zooniverse is the Internet’s largest citizen science platform, with over 3 million users over time. They take difficult computational problems that humans are good at, such as reading bad handwriting, identifying plant and animal species, recognising patterns, annotating images or differentiating astronomical phenomena, and enabling volunteers on the Internet (‘citizen scientists’) to participate in solving those problems, thus generating results and data that can support scientific and research projects around the world. Conversely it also offers a powerful resource to scientists, by enabling them to solve human data problems and outsource effort to the ‘wisdom of the crowd’ in order to further their own research agenda.

The Zooniverse is **not** a data collective per our definition in 1.1. The vast majority of the data handled is not personal data⁹¹, which means there is no data subject or serious duty to them (albeit the platform does have some duty to its volunteer users and project

⁹¹ At the extreme individual judgments contributed to train a machine learning system could be considered to be personal data, but it could be anonymized very quickly.

researchers). Nonetheless, it is a collective that does do work with data, of a different nature. And as such, we can draw many insights from it that can help other collectives.

In particular:

- It exemplifies the difference between passive and active participation.
- It shows how collective members can donate brain power/time not just data
- It can help with the goal of increasing impact potential, by observing how it has grown and built such a massive member base.
- It shows that collectives have a need of, and benefit from, building communities, and offers a blueprint for how this can be done
- It shows how attention can be gained for collective work/projects (for example, through platformisation/project builder tools, through gamification of tasks, and through through to participation in TV events like BBC Stargazing Live)
- It shows the importance of structured protocols and effective interfaces to shaping participation (through its workflows for volunteer participation)
- It shows the need to fund infrastructure and development resources (and the ability to do so collectively, as it has done through its multiple host institutions, grants, and bespoke services offerings)
- It shows the value of tooling to help people make sense of data (and for them to then help machines make sense of data - cyclical!) much like Digipower Academy
- It shows insights into motivation for participation - e.g. gamification, intermittent reward, altruistic framing, etc.
- It shows an example of the impact and value that collective(s) can create and have created - advancing science, publications, helping society (as well as delivering individual benefits).

4. Enabling and Nurturing Data Collectives

While Section 2 explained what collectives do, and Section 3 explained the effects that collectives can have, this section shifts focus to that of an external organisation that wishes to help a data collective to flourish.

We will describe ways in which collectives can be enabled through data, as well as through other sorts of support including skills development, infrastructure, help with publicity, reach, and through introducing the collective to other organisations that can help them access new capabilities or enable mutually beneficial collaborations.

This section builds upon the change model presented in 1.4, so we recommend a review of Figure 1 and Figure 2 before reading. As a reminder, the four quadrants of change we explained in 1.4 are:

- **Collective/Internal:** Where the goal is to collectively acquire knowledge and new understandings.
- **Collective/External:** Where collective work aims to protect and enhance people's capabilities in society through innovation or activism.
- **Individual/External:** Where collectives seek to influence individual relationships with organisations and structures in society
- **Individual/Internal:** Where collectives seek to influence and transform individuals' ways of thinking and reasoning about personal data and about data holders.

Based on these four quadrants, we will in section 4 introduce a more advanced mental model for thinking about how to support data collectives, which we call the **Data Enablement Cube**. We will build up an explanation of this concept through the following subsections, culminating in the illustration of the cube concept in 4.4.

4.1 Enabling Collective Action Through Data

Figure 4: An illustration of "Data Enablement" for a collective. The top square is split into four quadrants, as a reminder that the collective is pursuing theme-focused change along some combination within its own theory of change of the four ToC dimensions.

As the example stories in Section 3 show, a collective will succeed through its ability to act, and to achieve impactful results from its actions; with the ToC model introduced in Section 1. That impact can be measured in terms of achieving change in people and organisations' thinking, behaviours or structures.

Therefore, to support a collective means two things:

- 1) Improving its collective intelligence (Section 1.2), its internal effectiveness;
- 2) Improving its ability to take collective action (see Section 2.4), and in so doing to have impact upon people, organisations, and society.

We believe that both objectives can be helped, by undertaking work to **data enable** the collective.

We define **data enablement** as:

- Increasing a collective's ability to obtain, interpret and use personal data to acquire knowledge and pursue its goals; and
- Increasing a collective's ability to understand, collaborate, challenge, disrupt and exert influence upon and within the data economy

In other words, the more connected and knowledgeable a collective is to the worlds of individuals' personal data and the ecosystems that hold, use, share and trade that data, the more they can increase their collective intelligence and ability to take collective action. Data enablement is what changes a collective that doesn't use data into an empowered data collective.

In Figure 4 above, we illustrate the concept of data enablement, depicted as a vertical axis or spectrum of capability. If we consider that collectives typically 'live' at the top of this axis, and that at the bottom of the diagram lives a 'sea' of personal data, that could potentially be accessed and tapped into for value and insight, then we can consider the data enablement of a collective as a "reaching down" into the data layer. It is not that a collective lives at a lower layer, more connected with data – it will still need to remain focused on themes in order to make itself relatable to the public, work on specific agendas and be fundable. Instead, we can consider that a more data-enabled collective will be able to choose to 'reach down' into the data, for certain activities where it is useful; and the more data enabled a collective, the more data (and thus, value/knowledge) it can access.

An important aspect of data-enablement is increasing a collective's ability to reach beyond its own thematic focus area. This is why the top of the axis is marked as "theme-focused". Most collectives and data collectives are specialised in narrow areas,

in terms of the types of personal data they deal with, the fields of human endeavour they situate themselves in, the potential returns they offer to their members, and the value they offer to society. For example, there are data collectives focused on gig economy worker rights, on health data sharing, on making democracy fairer, and on social media platform accountability. Each collective works with its members and partners effectively within that field, but through data (which, given it can provide a broad window across different parts of a user's life), there is the potential to unify collective efforts, because others in different sectors (or infrastructural software and services companies serving multiple sectors) can unlock new, broader ways of acquiring knowledge or motivating change in others. Becoming more data enabled does not mean abandoning a thematic focus; but it can benefit from "lifting your head up" and looking beyond the collective's own specific thematic area to identify opportunities for collaboration and mutual benefits, especially through personal data storage, unification, interpretation and innovative use. An external organisation working with multiple collectives is well placed to improve data enablement in this way.

4.2 Approaches to Supporting Collectives and Data Collectives

Considering the four quadrants of change (see section 4 intro above and 1.4), we can now consider what data enablement might look like in each quadrant, and how an external organisation can help collectives to become more data enabled.

Individual/Internal ("Educate & Empower")

In this quadrant, the goal is to influence and transform individuals' ways of thinking and reasoning about personal data and about data holders. The focus therefore is on knowledge transfer, and a supporting organisation can help with that goal.

For example, a collective may wish to work with educating individuals (which could be members of the collectives or beneficiaries of its work) to be able to use their data access rights to obtain their personal data, or to work in schools or workplaces to raise awareness of data literacy skills updated for the personal data economy era⁹². A support

⁹² 'Data literacy' traditionally includes a focus on critical thinking skills and being able to carry out numerical analysis and construct arguments using data. Alex Bowyer's thesis (see footnote 22) offers an updated version of 'data literacy' for the personal data economy era, which highlights the need for individuals to develop not just these skills but also additional skills around:

organisation could facilitate such training and education opportunities for the wider civic society, for example through connections with schools, local authorities or business networks.

One way in which such knowledge transfer can occur is through press releases, social media and traditional media and public relations routes. Journalistic coverage can raise awareness of current data-centric service provider practices, or of new tools, capabilities and rights that individuals may have.

Ultimately the goal here is to give people courage and motivation to embrace the personal data economy landscape, and this may be pursuable by a broad civic organisation more easily than a specific collective; indeed such an organisation could potentially run its own public education initiatives without depending upon theme focused collectives. Of course, such collectives can still help illustrate the message and make it more relatable to the public. In general, expressing a message in terms of the personal impact of data can improve the relatability of the message. Individuals can recognise empowerment through the idea that they might gain more capabilities over the data that represents information about their life and affects the decisions that shape their lives. Such an everyday-life-centric focus can also make data more relatable to the public and increase demand for better access, rights and capabilities in the personal data landscape.

Individual/External (“Influence & Motivate”)

In this quadrant, the focus is upon influencing individuals and organisations (including service providers, governments and regulators) to change their relationships with each other.

-
- being able to appreciate the intrinsic value of your personal data as containing stored facts and records about your life;
 - being able to understand the implications of how your personal data is used and shared by organisations you interact with (your personal data ecosystem);
 - having an appreciation of the importance of establishing portable data and separation between data and platforms/services;
 - knowing how to exercise your rights to obtain your own data, being able to recognise incomplete data returns and knowing how to demand corrections or better responses; and
 - understanding the need for a free and fair information landscape and being able to identify when your individual agency is being diminished.

The role for a supporting organisation here can be in helping a collective to connect with the public so that the collective might more easily launch and drive adoption as they launch new tools, websites, services or campaigns that can offer people new ways to interact with personal data, with DPOs/personal data holding organisations, with regulators, with political representatives.

A supporting organisation may also be able to help with publicity or funding around the promotion of data-related actions (such as ‘request your data’ or ‘contribute your data to this collective’) or the showcasing of new data behaviours or tools.

A supporting organisation could also use their influence with business partners, civil servants, regulators, local authorities, parliamentary representatives or other authority figures, to help collectives get their message heard and acted upon.

Collective/Internal (“Learn & Discover”)

In this quadrant, the focus is upon acquiring knowledge and new understandings through group activities. A supporting organisation can provide support by helping the collective to increase its access to, and ability to gather, interpret, and learn from data, about people, and about the behaviours of data holders in the data economy.

One of the major tasks a collective needs to do in order to explore personal data, is to establish a safe and secure place to combine that data, while respecting any consent and anonymity considerations. A supporting organisation can help fund service provision, can connect collectives to other collectives that might be developing similar systems (and thus save costs), or could (directly or indirectly) provide legal, operation or technical advice around issues of consent and data security.

This is the quadrant in which research takes place. Through the funding of ventures such as digitrails, digipower, and indeed this report, as well as supporting more traditional research (for example in the MyData landscape, or in HDI academic research laboratories) the entire data collective sector can be helped in its data enablement from an understanding and knowledge and acquisition perspective - for example knowledge about what data holders do with personal data, or how that knowledge can be used to respond.

External organisations could also help fund tools and development organisations who are developing data exploration and insight tooling, and data audit capabilities;

increasing collectives' capability to gather quantitative data about actors in the personal data economy landscape.

Collective/External (“Defend & Create”)

In this quadrant, collectives focus on protecting and improving the status quo, the legal and social operating conditions in which collectives (as all organisations) operate. This is another area where an external organisation can provide assistance.

For example, a supporting organisation could help support new interoperability standards and technologies to help collectives gain leverage to act in the ecosystem. This could be through funding or through political campaigning.

A supporting organisation could work with legislators, regulators and policymakers to support the creation of better access rights and policy innovation (for example, helping people to gain ongoing data visibility, or better explainability of personal data use).

An external organisation with good civic contacts might be able to add weight and influence to collective's attempts to influence data holders or to make complaints to regulators or to lobby politicians in individual or collective cases.

An organisation with grant-awarding or funding capability could support the innovative research and development of new personal data technologies, such as personal data lockers or personal data understanding tools such as those made in Digipower Academy.

A well connected support organisation could also help to introduce or connect together different complementary groups working on different parts of the data ecosystem landscape, for example connecting together tech projects, collectives, innovators, and journalists to increase impact/societal change.

A well respected tech industry body might be able to represent the collective interests of multiple collectives in discussions with tech companies

4.3 Extending a Data Collective's Reach and Potential Impact

In Section 4.2 we examined the question of supporting a data collective through the lens of the four change quadrants. However there are some commonalities. Across all four

quadrants, one of the most obvious ways to help is through funding assistance to collectives. We will talk more about that in section 5, but what is important is that the funding is smartly directed towards the right things (and a focus on specific quadrants can be useful for this).

However, data collectives exist in a wider ecosystem, which includes other collectives, personal data economy or data-analysis focused companies and groups, technical service providers, regulators, politicians, journalists, legislators and local and national government representatives and more. A collective's ability to produce a change in society will always be limited if they act alone. Through working together (either with other collectives⁹³ or with large numbers of individuals (see 3.2), their potential to execute effective collective action that produces change is increased. This is where a supporting organisation can be of great help to a collective, in increasing its reach and public profile. Collectives need amplifying, so that they might be heard by established decisionmakers and by the public. This is more than just standard marketing or public relations, because it requires a degree of persuasion and empathy-building toward their causes.

Looking at efforts described in 4.2 together, we can see that these many ideas for how an external organisation might help a collective – especially funding, but also tactical networking, public relations, innovation and research – the *impact potential* of a data collective can be increased. Increasing the attention and reach of a collective, can generate new demand, interest, and opportunities for collaboration, which can open up opportunities to create new and powerful capabilities for the individuals that the collectives serve, and collectives that are more able to secure change for their members and beneficiaries.

To mention a small example, the MAZE collective in Paris⁹⁴ brings together Uber drivers to improve their employment conditions. By becoming data enabled they have managed to pool journey data from their driver members to gain new insights; and they are now working outwards within the ecosystem to create a new opportunity: to sell their aggregate movement data statistics to regional authorities. They have created a secondary market, providing them with a business model to help fund future collective work and also unlocking new opportunities for collaboration with local authorities and with business partners such as Hestia.ai.

⁹³ <https://www.radicalxchange.org/>

⁹⁴ <https://www.maze.cab/>

As we look back at the ecosystem-focused perspective we have explored here in Section 4.3, we can see that data enablement is not just about internal effectiveness with data, but a distinct second aspect of external effectiveness at large in society.

For this reason, it is useful to think not of “supporting a collective to help itself climb to success”, but instead to think of the ecosystem of society “reaching down a hand to help pull the collective up”. This mindset emphasises a focus not on the collective itself, but on **optimising the conditions for success** that exist in the legal, sociotechnical and political landscape. This can change a support organisations thinking from “How do we equip each of these collectives we want to help so that they can fight more effectively for their cause” to “How can we use our own capabilities to improve the environment in which these collectives operate?” It frees the support organisation to work independently to improve the digital power landscape, through the pursuit of better rights, better laws, better education, better tooling, better standards and infrastructure, better driving of understanding and demand for new models of data relationships and data interaction. Through focusing its efforts on the landscape that exists, a supporting organisation can help multiple data collectives simultaneously to become more data enabled and more able to exert effective collection action that can create lasting change.

4.4 The Data Enablement Cube: A model for supporting data collectives to flourish

In this section, we unify the ideas presented throughout sections Sections 1.4 and 4.1 to 4.3, to present the **Data Enablement Cube**, the mental model we offer for how to think about how to support collectives.

Figure 5: The Data Enablement Cube: A model for the flourishing of data collectives. Collectives can achieve different levels of data-enablement in the four different Change Quadrants, unlocking new activities they can carry out to help pursue their thematic goals.

In Figure 5, we present the Data Enablement Cube. The top face is focused on theme-centred activities, with the “data enablement” / reaching down concept from Figure 4 (in section 4.1) – shown as the vertical/z axis spreading down towards the sea of data the collective wishes to make use of. This is split over four columns, extending down from the four quadrants present on the top face, representing the ToC quadrants (Figure 1 & 2 in section 1.4). These quadrants are also shown here (and labeled) on the bottom face.

As the cube shows, a collective can be differently data enabled in one, two, three, or four quadrants simultaneously, and to varying degrees; it depends what kinds of changes they wish to pursue. A supporting organisation can focus simply on enabling a collective

to operate, act or to have impact within a particular quadrant; or in multiple parallel endeavours across quadrants.

This presents a useful reminder, both for the collective's own internal strategic planning, but also for any supporting organisation, that investment of effort and resources can be consciously directed towards particular activities in particular quadrants, and that any one of those activities could become a more data enabled activity.

It is particularly gainful to consider that once access to data is achieved, that data can quickly become useful for other quadrants. For example, some data about provider behaviours with personal data might be at first beneficial for enlightening an individual member (I/I quadrant), but that same data can quickly become useful for convincing other individuals in the collective (C/I quadrant), or for external advocacy (I/E then C/E).

Often this extension to other quadrants will come through secondary uses, and consent must be considered carefully, for example what data a collective member has contributed into the collective for personal insight or aggregate statistics, might not be something they are willing to see used in a public relations effort. But the connections between different quadrants can be made, as shown by the double-ended horizontal arrows in the diagram, either within one collective or across different collectives. For example, a tool developed to help change data interface practices (Collective/External) may also be useful as an educational tool (internal/individual), or some data collected by one collective may also hold value that would be useful to another collective (given suitable consent). Support organisations can help facilitate the establishment of such data-sharing relationships and infrastructure.

The cross-quadrant emulation is essential to the value of a collective, and can be truly unifying across civil society. For instance, many local labour unions might defend different arguments across cities concerning platform work, but just a few individual workers recovering their own data can help construct a completely new narrative, starting with documentation of undeniable evidence extending all the way towards innovation of new business models. **Key in this emulation across quadrants is the ability to jump from the individual to the collective, and the internal to the external. This will be facilitated by experimenting very locally, for local matters, and in societies that are quite "flat" with very shallow hierarchies.**

We hope that this cube is a powerful takeaway from this report; a visual reminder of the key messages around how to support collectives: to focus on specific quadrants, but

also to focus on data enablement (both of data access, and of ecosystem negotiability/influence) within each quadrant.

5. Funding and Sustainability

Data collectives face tremendous obstacles: they need to simultaneously develop a new culture among their members, acquire a wide diversity of skills (technical, legal, advocacy, literacy), they need to maintain trust, they need to handle data security, etc.

All this is extremely costly, so there should be an intense focus throughout on cost reduction:

- expand the work of an existing collective towards the use of data, don't create a data collective from scratch;
- if new tools are needed, make sure they are built with free software licenses, and ideally financed jointly.

Additionally, even assuming the data collective work is grafted on top of an existing theme-focused collective, thought should be given on revenue generation.

For this purpose, it is important to connect individuals to their data quickly (through visualizations, for instance), as this helps in expanding the range of individuals and entities, internal and external to the collective, able to imagine new forms of contributions and returns, thereby expanding the funding opportunities.

Given the highly skilled nature of the work and the need to preserve trust (excluding e.g. selling members' data), it is probable that those funding opportunities will first develop nearest the top of the DIKW pyramid (data-information-knowledge-wisdom, Section 2). Consultancy, research and training work towards a wide class of commercial and non-profit actors can generate a virtuous cycle of contributions - in fact combining simultaneously the data enablement of the collective with the generation of new revenue. Additionally, collaborating with entities also focused on knowledge production (such as academic projects), but with a more participative approach (citizen science) might be a way to bootstrap the funding of projects.

Business-to-government data sharing schemes (B2G) will also be fruitful areas around which to explore, from a funding perspective:

- B2G dataflows require tooling, and the state can mobilize funds for services supporting those flows;
- at the same time not all flows should be enabled: most often governments only need aggregate data while there are privacy concerns at individual level (e.g. mobility patterns);

From this tension one could wonder if some B2G schemes would not be best replaced with B2C{consumer, citizen}2G, or B2C{consumer,citizen}2NGO schemes. Systematic exploitation of such situations leads to a nucleus opening up the possibility of standing “in the middle” a proper data collective.

Finally, in some cases, collectives that have a member-based business model might be a good fit for prototyping some projects, as they already generate revenue from membership and their interests are fully aligned with their members (hence we can presume some level of trust is already present). One would only needs to offer members additional beneficial services through data to justify some form of premium membership level. Note that in this case the first use of the data would be for individual benefit, and the collective benefit would come second.

6. Recommendations

We have considered in this text many different aspects relevant to experimentation around data collectives:

- the motivation for standing up a data collective (Section 2), and in particular the three possible philosophies (Capitalist, “Common Good”, Individualist, in Section 2.3) and the three paradigms of collective work (Investigative, Education, Activist, in Section 2.4);
- the impact areas of the data collective (with many thematic examples in Section 3);
- the relevance of a pair of theories of change, appearing as top and bottom face in a Data Enablement Cube (Section 4.4);
- business considerations (Section 5).

The hardest in this area is doing things the first time around. There are two reasons this is hard: because the work involves wide collaborations in order to reach sustainability

(even bottom-up efforts need institutional partners), and because it requires motivating people from the general public with only abstract and imagined end benefits at first.

This naturally leads to the following two recommendations:

Recommendation 1: aim to build many completely different small experiments, involving as few partners as necessary to establish the value of creating new dataflows with a data collective involved. This is because one can presume “patching” those experiments together afterwards will be easier, through emulation between data collectives, once that value is proven.

Recommendation 2: aim for each separate experiment to require as few data contributors as possible in order to establish the value of creating new dataflows. “Scaling” those experiments together afterwards should not be a concern: once that value is proven, emulation between data contributors will solve the issue.

Recommendation 3: aim for each separate experiment to be built around an existing membership based thematic collectives, and add a data dimension as described with the Data Enablement Cube.

Recommendation 4: from the perspective of this membership-based thematic collective (such as an NGO), assess B2G trends and see if there is not an opportunity to spin instead a B2C2NGO2G scheme.

Considering now the motivations for standing up a data collective, the paradigms and philosophies:

Recommendation 5: focus on membership-based thematic collectives who strike a good balance between educational and investigative focus, as well as individualist and common good focus.

This is because the educational components will help in making recruitment more of a peer-to-peer process, thereby reducing effort and costs. The rest of the recommendation is to “thread the middle path” and avoid more extreme slants (capitalism philosophy because it breeds distrust at the moment in relation to personal data, and activist paradigm because many are quick to dismiss much activism around data as passé in light of technical progress).

Recommendation 6: focus on membership-based thematic collectives who encourage local participation.

Local participation is important as it breeds trust and facilitates a lot of the previous actions in general (in a small town, local government is closer and you need less data contributors for those efforts to reach relative critical mass).

So far we have left aside the question of the theme to consider. While acknowledging funders tend to silo their contribution into themes, this is suboptimal from the perspective of the data.

Recommendation 7: include one experiment where geolocation data is relevant (e.g. mobility), because this is the easiest starting point pedagogically, which expands the range of communication opportunities in order to further that experiment's goals.

Recommendation 8: work actively on transferring insight, tooling and best practices from such a data collective operating around geolocation data contributions, to other data collectives (e.g. on desinformation). In other words, piggyback on people's and partner's understanding around a geolocation data collective to accelerate the work of other data collectives.

Recommendation 9: Through proper documentation and communications, accelerate emulation:

- between the types of experiment;
- between locales where such an experiment is deployed;
- between data contributors;
- between themes.